

STRUCTURAL IMPROVEMENT OF THE CARRIAGE ASSEMBLY IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE NF-630 MILLING MACHINE INTO THE NF- 1200 MODEL

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Abstract

This thesis analyzes the structural improvement of the carriage assembly during the modernization of the NF-630 milling machine into the NF-1200 model. The main purpose of modernization is to expand the technological capabilities of the existing machine, create the possibility of machining large-sized parts, and increase the accuracy and rigidity of the table-carriage system. According to the passport data of the NF-1200 milling machine, the machine is capable of machining workpieces with dimensions of $1200 \times 500 \times 500$ mm and a weight of up to 800 kg. Therefore, the carriage assembly was redesigned, and its support base, guide surfaces, and fastening elements were improved. As a result, the machining area of the machine was expanded, the accuracy of coordinate movement was improved, and the efficient use of the existing production base was ensured.

Keywords: NF-630, NF-1200, milling machine, modernization, carriage, table-carriage system, CNC machine, machining accuracy.

Introduction

Increasing production efficiency in the machine-building industry and machining large-sized parts with high accuracy require the use of modern technological equipment. In particular, during milling, drilling, boring, and threading operations on housing-type and base-type parts, the working area of the machine, the load-carrying capacity of the table, the movement accuracy of the carriage, and structural rigidity are of great importance.

In practice, replacing existing machine tools with new ones is not always an economically convenient solution. Therefore, expanding the technological capabilities of existing machines through modernization is considered an urgent

issue for manufacturing enterprises. This thesis examines the process of adapting the NF-630 milling machine to the NF-1200 model, with particular attention to the structural improvement of the carriage assembly.[1]

The NF-1200 milling machine modernized on the basis of the NF-630 milling machine was selected as the research object. The general view of the machine is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General view of the NF-1200 milling machine
Necessity of Modernization

The existing structural capabilities of the NF-630 milling machine were not sufficient for machining large-sized parts. In particular, the dimensions, load-carrying capacity, and travel range of the table-carriage system created limitations in placing large workpieces. Therefore, it became necessary to modernize the machine in accordance with the technical requirements of the NF-1200 model.

The carriage is one of the main structural elements of the machine, supporting the table and moving it along the Y-axis. The geometric accuracy, rigidity, and arrangement of the guide surfaces of this assembly directly affect the final accuracy of the machined part. The existing carriage design of the NF-630 machine is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Working drawing of the carriage assembly of the NF-630 milling machine

Structural Improvement of the Carriage Assembly

One of the most important structural solutions in the modernization process was the redesign of the carriage assembly in accordance with the requirements of the NF-1200 model. The new carriage was designed to work with a longer and wider working table. In this design, the guide surfaces, mounting holes, and support zones were rearranged.

In the NF-1200 model, the carriage performs the following main functions: it serves as a support for mounting the table and moving it along the X-axis; it moves the table-carriage system along the Y-axis; it receives the load from the weight of the machined workpiece; it ensures movement accuracy and structural rigidity; and it provides coordinate motion together with the ball screw pair and linear

guideways. The working drawing of the modernized carriage assembly is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Working drawing of the modernized carriage assembly adapted to the NF-1200 model

Compared with the NF-630 carriage design, several structural changes were implemented in the NF-1200 carriage assembly. First, the length of the carriage and its support base were increased. This makes it possible to stably support the working table with a length of 1200 mm. Second, the guide surfaces were strengthened and the arrangement of the linear guideways was optimized. This ensures movement accuracy between the table and the carriage during the machining of heavy workpieces.

Third, the number and arrangement of the mounting holes were redesigned. This provides reliable fastening of the carriage to the machine base and helps reduce vibrations during the machining process. Fourth, the cast body and support surfaces of the carriage were enlarged, which increased its structural rigidity. As a result, deformation under load is reduced and machining accuracy is improved.[2]

Main Technical Parameters

The NF-1200 milling machine is designed for milling, drilling, boring, and threading operations on housing-type and base-type parts made of ferrous and

non-ferrous metals, as well as some plastic materials. As a result of modernization, the main technical capabilities of the machine were formed as follows:

Indicator	Value
Working table size	1200 × 500 mm
Maximum dimensions of the workpiece	1200 × 500 × 500 mm
Maximum workpiece weight	800 kg
Travel along the X-axis	1000 mm
Travel along the Y-axis	450 mm
Travel along the Z-axis	500 mm
Feed rate range	1–4000 mm/min
Positioning accuracy	0.02 mm
Positioning stability	0.01 mm
Spindle speed range	80–3550 rpm
Maximum torque	500 N·m
Machine weight	7000 kg

These indicators show that the NF-1200 model is adapted for machining larger-sized parts. In particular, the 1200 × 500 mm working table and the ability to machine workpieces weighing up to 800 kg expand the field of application of the machine in production.

Results and Discussion

As a result of modernizing the NF-630 machine into the NF-1200 model, the technological capabilities of the machine were significantly expanded. The most important result was the increase in the working table surface to 1200 × 500 mm and the creation of the possibility to machine workpieces with dimensions of 1200 × 500 × 500 mm. This made the machine suitable for machining large housing-type and base-type parts.

The redesign of the carriage assembly provided several technological advantages. First, the possibility of placing large-sized workpieces was increased. Second, the required support rigidity for machining workpieces weighing up to 800 kg was ensured. Third, the accuracy of coordinate movement along the X and Y axes was improved. Fourth, the overall stability of the table-carriage system was increased.[3]

According to the passport data of the NF-1200 machine, the positioning accuracy is 0.02 mm, while the positioning stability is 0.01 mm. These indicators show that the modernized table-carriage system can operate with sufficient accuracy. In addition, the machine has a feed rate range from 1 to 4000 mm/min along the X, Y, and Z axes. This makes it possible to perform rough milling, semi-finishing, and final finishing operations.

Another important aspect of modernization is related to economic efficiency. By using the existing NF-630 base, the cost of purchasing a new machine is reduced, while production capabilities are expanded. Therefore, modernization can be considered a technically and economically reasonable solution.

Conclusion

The modernization of the NF-630 milling machine into the NF-1200 model is one of the effective ways to expand the technological capabilities of existing production equipment. The results of the study show that the most important structural change in the modernization process is related to the carriage assembly. This assembly plays a key role in increasing the working table size, improving the load-carrying capacity, and ensuring the accuracy of coordinate movement.

As a result of modernization, the machine became capable of machining workpieces with dimensions of 1200 × 500 × 500 mm and weighing up to 800 kg. Travel distances of 1000 mm, 450 mm, and 500 mm along the X, Y, and Z axes, respectively, were provided. This increases the practical importance of the NF-1200 model in machining housing-type, base-type, and large machine-building parts.

In general, the modernization of the NF-630 machine into the NF-1200 model is a technically, technologically, and economically reasonable solution. It contributes to the efficient use of the existing production base, reduces the cost of purchasing new equipment, and expands production capabilities.

References:

1. Ataullaev A., Ataullaev O., Juraev N., Isaev D. Control Mechanism for the Rotational Support System of an Antenna // Proceedings of the IV International Conference on Advances in Materials, Earth Science, and Technology AIP Conf. Proc. 3390, 060030-1-060030-8; <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0322334>.
2. Isaev D., Khamidov B., Ataullaev A., Ravshanov J., Juraev N. Comparative Analysis of Wear-Resistant Coating on Carbide end Mills Using Vibrodiagnostic Method // Proceedings of the IV International Conference on Advances in Materials, Earth Science, and Technology AIP Conf. Proc. 3390, 020016-1-020016-7; <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0322333>

3. A.O. Ataulaev, O.X. Ataulaev, F.A. Ergashev Automated rectification of pulse response characteristics in radio engineering two-stage amplifiers //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – T. 417. – pp. 05007

